

Mixed Ligand Thiocyanato Complexes of Cobalt(II)-Coordination Number Six and Eight

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Dithiocyanato bis-(2-aminobenzothiazole) Cobalt(II) complex- $\text{Co}(\text{ABT})_2(\text{SCN})_2$ was reacted with a variety of nitrogen donor ligands in a mixed solvent medium. One hexa-coordinated compound- $\text{Co}(\text{ABT})_2(\text{SCN})_2\text{Py}_2$ - and three octa-coordinated complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{ABT})_2(\text{SCN})_2\text{L}_4]$ where $\text{L} = \beta$ -picoline, γ -picoline and isoquinoline, were isolated and characterised by analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectroscopy and thermal decomposition.

THE chemistry of thiazole system has been extensively studied as the C^2 of the thiazole ring is the active site of vitamin B_1 (Thiamin Pyrophosphate)^{1,2}. Also several metal complexes with substituted benzothiazoles,³ have been recently described. The substituents at 2,4 and 5 positions of the benzothiazole ring modify both the stoichiometry and the stereochemistry of the complexes^{4,5}. It is known⁶ that in thiocyanato complexes various factors like the effect of other ligands including their basicity and steric hindrance, π -bonding and preparative conditions control the mode of bonding of the ion to the metal. Cobalt(II) has a $3d^7$ non-bonding shell and usually forms tetrahedral or octahedral complexes utilising $4s4p^3$ or $4s4p^54d^2$ bonding orbitals. But the possibility of its exhibiting higher coordination numbers can not be ruled out under favourable ligand environment and experimental conditions. In this communication, Cobalt(II) complexes wherein the metal ion is surrounded by 2-aminobenzothiazole, thiocyanate, pyridine or substituted pyridine are studied and reported.

Experimental

Preparation of $[\text{Co}(\text{ABT})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$:

Dithiocyanato bis-(2-aminobenzothiazole) Cobalt (II) was prepared by the procedure described in the literature⁵ and characterised by estimating the metal and the thiocyanate.

Preparation of $[\text{Co}(\text{ABT})_2(\text{SCN})_2\text{L}_2]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{ABT})_2(\text{SCN})_2\text{L}_4]$:

To a hot ethanolic solution of dithiocyanato bis-(2-aminobenzothiazole) Cobalt(II), slightly more than the stoichiometric amounts of nitrogen donor ligands were added separately followed by the addition of Carbon tetrachloride (2/1 v). Immediately the colour changed from royal blue to pink. On refluxing the contents for nearly an hour and

cooling, crystalline compounds separated out. In case of isoquinoline complex, the volume was reduced and then kept over night to get the product. These were filtered, washed with ethanol, petroleum ether and dried over calcium chloride *in vacuo*.

Physical measurements :

The purity of the complexes was established by estimating the metal and thiocyanate by standard methods. The conductance measurements were carried out on M/1000 solutions in acetone using a Toshniwal Conductivity bridge type CL 0102 and a dip type cell. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens using Gouy balance. Infrared absorptions were recorded on nujol and hexachlorobutadiene mulls using Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra in acetone were recorded using Unicam SP-500 and Carl Zeiss PMQ II Spectrophotometers. Thermogravimetric studies were carried out in a manually operated thermobalance. Analytical and physical data for complexes are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds are paramagnetic with μ_{eff} values ranging between 4.96 and 5.11 BM (Table-1). They are all spin free and the magnetic measurements indicate the presence of three unpaired electrons, the higher values being due to orbital contribution. For 1 : 1 electrolytes, the Δ_M values in acetone medium will be as high as 150 mhos⁷ and the low values obtained now indicate that they are essentially non-electrolytes but undergo appreciable dissociation in solution.

Infrared Spectra :

Thiazole is formally derived from imidazole by replacement of NH by S in 1-position which makes

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA FOR MIXED LIGAND COBALT(II) COMPLEXES

Sl No.	Compounds	Colour & form	M. P. (°C)	% Cobalt		% Thiocyanate		Λ M (mhos)	μ _{eff} (B.M.)
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.		
1.	[Co(ABT) ₂ (SCN) ₂ (Y-pic) ₄]	Pink crystalline	175	6.90	6.93	13.62	13.65	31	5.09
2.	[Co(ABT) ₂ (SCN) ₂ (β-pic) ₄]	-do-	143	6.92	6.93	13.58	13.65	54	4.96
3.	[Co(ABT) ₂ (SCN) ₂ (IQ) ₄]	Red crystalline	162	5.89	5.95	11.63	11.70	67	5.05
4.	[Co(ABT) ₂ (SCN) ₂ (Py) ₂]	Pink crystalline	208	9.25	9.30	18.26	18.31	52	5.11

thiazole a better π-acceptor due to the availability of empty d orbitals on sulphur atom. For the structure outlined for thiazole and benzothiazole, it is expected that on coordination through either sulphur or nitrogen, C-S stretching vibration will increase, while C=N stretching frequency will remain almost unaltered or may increase slightly for metal-sulphur bonding and will decrease for metal-nitrogen bonding. Infrared spectra of the complexes

show the presence of strong absorption bands of both 2-aminobenzothiazole and nitrogen donor ligands, indicating definitely that they are mixed ligand complexes. As expected, the ligand absorption bands are modified as a result of bonding to the metal. Some bands are however masked in the absorption range of Nujol used as mulling agent. As pointed above benzothiazoles could coordinate to metal either through nitrogen or sulphur. In case of S-bonded benzothiazole, significant changes in the range of 600-1600 cm⁻¹ are shift of bands at 1475 cm⁻¹ due to ν(C-N) and at 667 cm⁻¹ due to ν(C-S) in the spectra of the free ligand. The C-S stretching frequency is shifted to a higher value on account of an increased dπ-dπ contribution between sulphur and the ring π-system⁸. In the present case, the bands at ~700-725 cm⁻¹ in the ν(C-S) region and at ~3270 cm⁻¹ in the ν(N-H) region are indicative of the presence of 2-aminobenzothiazole bonded through sulphur atom with non-involvement of amino group in the complex formation⁹. Further the C=N stretching vibration of 2-aminobenzothiazole at ~1500 cm⁻¹ got split and shifted to a higher frequency regions 1515-1565 cm⁻¹ indicating that it is not N-bonded since in case of N-bonding, the ν(C=N) would have been decreased. The appearance of bands at ~1620 cm⁻¹ region is due to the ν(C=N) of the heterocyclic base. The thiocyanate ion SCN⁻ is an ambidentate ligand and various modes of its coordination have been recently reviewed^{10,11}. In the present compounds ν(C-N) bands appear in the region 2040-2084 cm⁻¹ and ν(C-S) are observed in the region 690-760 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of S-bonded thiocyanate group.

Electronic Spectra :

The compounds undergo dissociation in solution which is evidenced by the pink solids giving blue solutions. Extra addition of the ligand to the compounds in solution does not seem to prevent this dissociation. The spectrum obtained is similar to that of a four coordinated species. In fact, the broad bands at ~16400 cm⁻¹ region with high extinction coefficients (ε value ranging between 1020-1330) can be assigned to 4A₂→4T₁(P) transition corresponding to ν₃ of a species having tetrahedral symmetry¹². Hence it is evident that in the solution stage, the complex has changed over to a tetrahedral form by dissociation. Attempts were made to prevent this dissociation in a solvent by recording the absorption using nujol mull filter paper technique. Here no absorption in the region corresponding to a tetrahedral or an octahedral symmetry was seen but no definite conclusion could be drawn regarding the coordination number. However, additional evidence was obtained from the thermogravimetric studies of the compounds.

Thermal Decomposition :

Thermal decomposition of pyridine complexes of Cobalt(II) halides was studied earlier¹³ where pyridine was found to be lost gradually. The thermal behaviour of the compounds under report can be schematically represented as follows :

Thus the thermal decomposition studies of octa-coordinated compounds reveal a stepwise loss of the heterocyclic bases leading to the formation of hexa-coordinated compounds which decompose further yielding the four-coordinated starting compound, $\text{Co}(\text{ABT})_2(\text{SCN})_2$. The weight losses and the analyses of the compounds after decomposition agree with the above formulation. Hence it is evident that the original compounds are octa-coordinated from which two moles of the nitrogen donor ligand are lost in the first stage to give hexa-coordinated compounds. However, x-ray studies alone can reveal the exact coordination number and the proposed stereochemistry of the complexes.

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